

Policy brief

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Deatnu Watershed Pathway Workshop

The RecoSal project

The RecoSal project aims to support collaborative governance for the recovery of a diverse Atlantic salmon population complex in the large River Teno catchment (Teno in Finnish, Tana in Norwegian, and Deatnu in Northern Sámi) in the northernmost Fennoscandia. Through the establishment of collaborations aiming towards the formation of a Living Lab user community, the project will connect knowledge production with salmon management, with a special emphasis on the development of population-specific, target-based assessments of genetically diverse salmon populations in a multicultural setting that values Indigenous and Local Knowledge (ILK) and rights. RecoSal will provide transdisciplinary advice for designing and implementing effective and socially robust governance and management practices with the aim of ecological conservation and recovery of depleted biodiversity.

Map illustrating the study area. The Deatnu River catchment basin (in yellow) is located between Finland and Norway.

Ice breakup at the Deatnu river. Photo: Kia Hansen

Pathway Workshop

A series of four co-design workshops have been arranged during the RecoSal project's implementation, where stakeholders have been informed and engaged, and where the project process have been decided upon in a participatory manner (Bjärstig and Brattland 2024, Bjärstig et al. 2024a), and visions and outcomes discussed (Bjärstig et al. 2024b). The aim is the establishment of a permanent and long-term collaboration among actors after the project ends (i.e., a Living Lab).

The Pathway Workshop continues the work already started in the previous Future Vision Workshop (Bjärstig et al. 2024b), by discussing how the visions then developed should be realized. The Pathway Workshop was held in collaboration with the MARGISTAR Cost Action (CA21125) and the MountResilience project at hotel Utsjoki in May 2025.

The Pathway Workshop was one of a series of events during the same week with a cross-border Salmon Dialogue, and the annual Teno information meeting organized by the Teno river fisheries district as the main events. The Salmon Dialogue was the second in a series of three dialogues organized by Joddu - the Wild Salmon Centre in collaboration with the Sharing our knowledge (UiT the Arctic University of Norway) and RecoSal (LUKE) projects and included participants from both the Finnish and Norwegian side of the border river (see photo above). As an introduction to the dialogue, a new report written by the Sámi local consultancy Árvil (Eriksen and Nuorgam 2025), on the challenges and potentials of local governance of the watershed, was presented by the Sámi Parliament of Norway (see photo to the right). The Pathway Workshop preceded the Teno information meeting, and participants of the workshop were invited and included persons that had attended the previous Future Vision Workshop, with new participants, as well.

Method

In total 14 people, including facilitators, participated in the Pathway Workshop. Participants were local residents from the Finnish side of the Deatnu river. After introduction to and summary of the previous Future Vision Workshop the participants were divided into one Finnish language group (group 1, led by Mikko Jokinen and Seija Tuulentie) and one Northern Sámi language group (group 2, led by Camilla Brattland and Laila Pellenec) to be run in parallel and working on the two different visions previous developed.

Photo from the Salmon Dialogue. Sandra Márjá West, political advisor to the Norwegian Sámi Parliament council, speaks during the Salmon Dialogue. To her right: Niilo Aikio, Julie Gjörtz Howden, Kjell Olav Guttorm, Benn Larsen, Sammol Lukkari, Tapio Hakaste, and Vesa Länsman. Photo: Mikko Jokinen

Magne Svineng, head of department, Norwegian Sámi Parliament, presents the Árvil report. Photo: Vegar Bæhr, Sámi Parliament

Sammol Lukkari wraps up outcomes of group 2. Photo: Mikko Jokinen

The two groups at the Pathway Workshop worked with two different visions, previously developed at the Future Vision Workshop in Utsjoki, October 2024. Now the participants were tasked to work with these visions and elaborate on how to achieve wanted future conditions. Both groups discussed the visions in light of what needs to be eliminated, reduced, raised and created to fulfill them.

Group 1, consisting of participants living mostly in the upper and middle part of the river (Utsjoki area), both Sámi and non-Sámi, focused on the vision *“We want the Tenojoki Valley to be a prosperous and uncontentious area in the future, easy to settle in and start a business. This is important for the vitality of the region and the wellbeing of its people, and it is achieved when there are thriving new businesses and people who feel welcome and at home in the area.”* This vision reflects problems such as how to stimulate the local economy and remove bureaucratic barriers between Finland (EU-country) and Norway (non-EU). Utsjoki and the Finnish side of the Deatnu valley was also seen as an area where newcomers are not always welcomed, or where it takes a lot of time to be accepted as a full member of the community. That might hinder the establishment of new businesses and the introduction of fresh ideas. Moreover, fishing and other uses of natural resources should be ecologically sound and sustainable.

Group 2, consisting of local Sámi people from the middle to the upper part of the river (Utsjoki area), focused on the vision *“Salmon in the Deatnu/Tana river is managed based on local and traditional Sámi knowledge, Sámi cultural values and their Indigenous rights.”*

The workshop participants were given visions to consider, which they had drafted in the previous Future Vision Workshop. Their task now was to assess what needed to be eliminated, reduced, raised, and created in order to achieve the situation defined in the vision. The picture shows the answers given by group 1.

Results

The two groups had very different views on what was presented and discussed, following the two different visions they worked with. A consensus was not always found between group members. Therefore, some results may only represent the views of individual participants. The text below reflects the issues raised in the discussions and are summarized in Box 1.

Group 1 focused mostly on the development opportunities of the municipality, and there were different views raised in order to achieve that. This group agreed that it is necessary to **eliminate** and **reduce** the factors hindering the development, like fear of change and overall attitude, unequal treatment between livelihoods, and the excessive influence of the state and central power. There are tensions between Sámi and non-Sámi people, which are detrimental to the atmosphere and development opportunities, and these tensions should be eliminated. The group **raised** the importance of following through on agreed plans—such as those for tourism development—and called for stronger decision-making power at the local level. Group 1 strongly agreed that there is a need to eliminate unnecessary administrative barriers in development. Unlike Group 2, Group 1 did not discuss the Teno salmon and its management very much, but they did agree that Deatnu river fishing licenses should be more easily available and that profitable business and market-based models should be **created** to support sustainable fishing. Furthermore, the group emphasized that profitable business and market-based models should be created.

Four local fishing associations from the Utsjoki area were represented in Group 2. As the vision of a management system based on Sámi rights is quite the opposite from the current state-governed system, the participants mostly agreed on the points of **elimination** and **reduction** of state power in salmon management. The participants also agreed on **raising** awareness of fishing for other species. When discussing new management bodies or solutions to be **created**, the participants pointed out that the four associations do not necessarily always agree with each other and that it would be difficult to create consensus among the diversity of groups along the riverbank. A group with the participation of the different fishing associations would be able to provide advice, but perhaps not make the final decisions.

Box 1. Summing up the key messages from the two groups at the Pathway Workshop.

Key messages at the Pathway Workshop

Group 1

Vision: We want the Tenjoki Valley to be a prosperous and uncontentious area in the future, easy to settle in and start a business. This is important for the vitality of the region and the wellbeing of its people, and it is achieved when there are thriving new businesses and people who feel welcome and at home in the area.

What needs to be...

Eliminated: The group considered that factors hindering development and which should be eliminated include fear of change, jealousy between actors, unequal treatment of different business sectors in administration, and positive discrimination (favoritism) towards the Sámi. The excessive influence of the state, central government, and Metsähallitus was raised as a problem. Official statements by the administration should not be interpreted as binding in the same way as legislation.

Reduced: The group saw that there should be less greed and pursuit of self-interest, and ignorance about where the municipality's tax revenue origins.

Raised: In the municipality of Utsjoki, there should be a stronger understanding of decision-making and commitment to agreed policies, particularly in the development of tourism. The municipality should lead development, support entrepreneurship and promote joint development. It is also important to understand the sources of tax revenue, the self-government of the Sámi region, the transfer of power to the local level, cooperation with Norway, building community spirit, increasing trust, open discussion, developing public transport and supporting traditional cultures.

Created: Utsjoki needs a change in attitude, accepting structural changes and seeking solutions to increase vitality. Profitable business and market-based models, such as in air transport, should be promoted. Routes should be marked on maps for safety and tourism reasons. The voices of residents must be heard, and dialogue must be increased. Information on recreational opportunities is needed on the municipality's website. It should be possible to purchase fish processing facilities, separate salmon fishing from other fishing, and 24-hour fishing licences from officials in person.

Group 2

Vision: Salmon in the Deatnu/Tana river is managed based on local and traditional Sámi knowledge, Sámi cultural values and their Indigenous rights.

What needs to be...

Eliminated: Practically abolish the colonialist fragmented Teno management system, including the economic policy for prioritizing the sports fishery, and the current state to state governance regime.

Reduced: Prejudices towards other fisher groups should be reduced. Reduce the cabin owners' rights so that fewer fishing permits are issued. Predators should be reduced in order to protect the salmon. If research cannot be trusted, then it should be reduced.

Raised: Salmon should be restored. There could even be more research, at least when it is very targeted. Raise awareness of fishing for other species.

Created: A heritage information center/local knowledge center should be set up, one that would be sitting as a partner in negotiation tables and have real influence on decisions and outcomes. A new management group or body with a basis in Sámi language and traditions needs to be created to replace the old ones. If it is not possible to create a group with the proper legitimacy and trust, the group should at least make recommendations that are taken properly into account by the authorities.

Summing up – reflections and recommendations

Based on lessons learned from the previous Future Vision Workshop, the groups were divided into languages groups at the Pathway Workshop from the start. Printed handouts of PowerPoints were made available from the onset, indicating a readiness to handle potential technical problems. The research team monitored the schedule of the discussions, giving each of the four aspects time enough to be discussed and elaborated upon in the groups, though there was not enough time to have a closing discussion with both groups in the end. This is something to consider when conducting this type of Pathway Workshop in other settings.

Group 1 concentrated on the development opportunities of the municipality and discussed challenges and actions needed to move forward. There were different views presented in the group, but the group agreed that the need for cooperation and team spirit between the residents should be increased, and the equal treatment of different livelihoods should be ensured. In addition, the shared opinion of the group was that the decision-making power should be just and done locally.

Group 2 developed a summarizing statement which stated that the current management situation is not acceptable if it is not changed to allow Sámi voices to be heard and influence the management decisions. Another main point was that Sámi traditional knowledge should be the foundation of management and restoration of the salmon stocks. A new dynamic governance structure to accomplish this is needed. Even though the groups had different points of view and discussed different visions from the start, both groups agreed that the decision-making should be done more locally and the effect of central power in Utsjoki should be reduced.

In all, the results from this Pathway Workshop confirm and validate results and recommendations from the previous workshops, where the request of the locals and Sámi to be able to influence the future salmon management in the area must be acknowledged by national decisionmakers in both Norway and Finland.

The RecoSal project is funded by the EU Biodiversa+ programme, through the Research Council of Finland, the Research Council of Norway, and Formas (Sweden). More information about the RecoSal project: Recovering diversity in salmon populations and cultures of fishing; the subarctic River Teno basin as a confluence and a Living Lab (RecoSal)

MARGISTAR (COST Action 21125) is a forum for knowledge synthesis, exchange, and co-creation that brings together scientists, stakeholders, and policymakers to collaboratively reflect on the challenges for sustainability in mountainous regions while moving progressively towards real-world solutions. More information about MARGISTAR: <https://margistar.eu/>

MountResilience is a Horizon Europe (101112876) funded project that supports European regions and communities located in mountainous areas to increase their capacity to adapt to climate change and to transition towards a climate-resilient society. More information about MountResilience: <https://mountresilience.eu/>

Almost ice-free Deatnu river. Photo: Mikko Jokinen

Further reading and references:

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